

A NEW HIERARCHICAL REINFORCEMENT: GRAFTING GRAPHENE OXIDE ONTO CARBON FIBER

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1 Introduction

Carbon based reinforcements including macroscopic carbon fiber, micro-scale carbon sheet and nano-scale carbon nanotube/fullerene/graphene, have stimulated tremendous interest in developing the light-weight and high performance polymer matrix composites.¹⁻³ Assembling macroscopic carbon fiber and micro-/nano-filler together (called grafting) will realize the hierarchical reinforcements. The hierarchical reinforcement, on one hand, could remarkably improve the interface shear strength of carbon fiber composite.^{4, 5} On the other hand, the hierarchical reinforcement could benefit the uniform dispersion of nano-scale reinforcement (resting on carbon fiber) in nanocomposites.⁶ The graphene or graphene oxide has more excellent mechanical properties and larger specific surface area than carbon nanotube, which opens up the new insight to assemble new hierarchical reinforcement. Larger specific surface area supplies stronger connection between CF and polymer. Meanwhile, the uniform distribution of GO on CF surface allows a good dispersion of GO in polymer around CF.

we proposed a new hierarchical reinforcement consisting of GO and CF. The GO was chemically and uniformly grafted onto CF, in between which the poly(amido amine) (PAMAM) dendrimer acted as the “bridge”, as shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1 Scheme: The schematic of grafting procedures.

2 Results and Discussion

2.1 Surface morphologies

Atomic force microscopy (AFM) (Fig. 2 (a)) reveals the thickness of wrinkled graphene oxide used for grafting is around 1.5 nm. The surface morphologies of CF before and after grafting GO were observed by field emission scanning electron microscope (FESEM), as shown in Fig. 2. We can see that different sizes GO sheets are attached to CF surface, which forms a new hierarchical structure. We zoomed in the hierarchical reinforcement and found that the most GO sheets were attached along the CF axial direction. Interestingly, quite a number of GO sheets are stably standing onto carbon fiber, as observed in Fig. 2. The size of GO sheets are micro-level and most of them are regular.

Fig. 2 (a)AFM image of graphene oxide, FESEM images for the CFs: (b) Acid-treated CF, (c) PAMAM-adsorbed CF, (d)(e)(f)(g) GO-grafted CF.

To explore the interface of the GO sheets on the CF, this new hierarchical structure was observed by transmission electron microscopy (TEM) as shown in Fig. 3. The GO stably stands on the CF surface, as shown in Fig. 3 (a), supplying the opportunity that GO could penetrate into the polymer matrix and locally stiffen the interface of the resulting

composites. The high magnification of the interface between GO sheet and CF was demonstrated in Fig. 3 (b). There a nano layer about 10 nm thick is visible between GO sheet and CF, which should be PAMAM layer. This reveals the direct evident that the new interface structure is CF-PAMAM-GO. Namely, the GO was grafted onto CF through PAMAM layer.

Fig. 3 TEM of GO-grafted CF

2.2 Surface chemical analysis

Fig. 4 XPS curve fitting of (a) C1s peak (b) N1s peak.

The elemental chemical states of grafting process were assessed by X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS). The results conclude the chemical reactions happened between PAMAM and CF, GOs and PAMAM. Namely, the GOs were chemically grafted onto the CF by PAMAM bridging as shown in Fig. 4.

Fig. 5 (a) Contact angle of different CF samples for two liquids, (b) Surface free energy of different CF samples.

The surface free energy shows an obvious increase from 29.9 mJ/m² to 67.0 mJ/m² after the absorption of PAMAM onto CF in comparison with acid treated CF, and shows a little decrease from 67.0 mJ/m² to 59.7 mJ/m² after GO-grafted, as shown in Fig. 5. The new hierarchical reinforcement can acquire an improved interfacial wettability by massive functional groups and the surface topography. In summary, a new hierarchical reinforcement was realized by grafting GO sheets onto carbon fibers. The GO sheets are uniformly distributed onto CF. This new hierarchical reinforcement has potential application in high performance polymer composites with excellent interfacial properties.

References

- [1] T.-W. Chou, L. Gao, E. T. Thostenson, Z. Zhang, J.-H. Byun, An assessment of the science and technology of carbon nanotube-based fibers and composites. *Composites Science and Technology*, 70 (1), 1-19, 2010.
- [2] H. G. Chae, S. Kumar, Materials science - Making strong fibers. *Science*, 319 (5865), 908-909, 2008.
- [3] J. N. Coleman, U. Khan, W. J. Blau, Y. K. Gun'ko, Small but strong: A review of the mechanical properties of carbon nanotube-polymer composites. *Carbon*, 44 (9), 1624-1652, 2006.
- [4] V. P. Veedu, A. Y. Cao, X. S. Li, K. G. Ma, C. Soldano, S. Kar, P. M. Ajayan, M. N. Ghasemi-Nejhad, Multifunctional composites using reinforced laminae with carbon-nanotube forests. *Nature Materials*, 5 (6), 457-462, 2006.
- [5] H. Qian, E. S. Greenhalgh, M. S. P. Shaffer, A. Bismarck, Carbon nanotube-based hierarchical composites: a review. *Journal of Materials Chemistry*, 20 (23), 4751, 2010.
- [6] S. Stankovich, D. A. Dikin, G. H. B. Dommett, K. M. Kohlhaas, E. J. Zimney, E. A. Stach, R. D. Piner, S. T. Nguyen, R. S. Ruoff, Graphene-based composite materials. *Nature*, 442 (7100), 282-286, 2006.